

Synthesis and characterization of *meso*-substituted triazonoporphyrins

Ranjan K. Bhatt, Dileep Kumar Singh and Mahendra Nath*

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007, India

E-mail : mnath@chemistry.du.ac.in Fax : 91-11-27666605

Manuscript received 17 October 2011, revised 03 September 2012, accepted 03 October 2012

Abstract : A simple one-pot three-component synthetic protocol for the construction of novel *meso*-substituted porphyrin-triazone conjugates has been developed. The reaction of 5-(4-aminophenyl)-10,15,20-triphenylporphyrin with formaldehyde and *N,N'*-disubstituted urea or thiourea derivatives in THF at reflux temperature afforded the corresponding new triazonoporphyrins in moderate yields. All the prepared products were characterized by IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectrometry.

Keywords : Synthesis, triazonoporphyrins, urea, thiourea, one-pot reaction.

Introduction

Porphyrins have received a considerable attention in recent years due to their vital role in various life sustaining processes¹. The versatile modification prospects of the porphyrin based precursors have proved their importance in various fields including photochemistry, catalysis, material chemistry and medicinal chemistry^{2,3}. In the last several decades, the porphyrin chemistry has been expanded to develop a series of novel macrocyclic compounds with porphyrin nucleus. Porphyrins having various functionalities at the periphery have been extensively used as precursors for the preparation of several complex molecules to mimic the essential features of natural photosynthetic systems⁴⁻⁶, and functions of various enzymes^{7,8}. They have also been developed as molecular-based materials for optoelectronics⁹, photovoltaic energy conversion¹⁰, catalysis¹¹, optical sensing^{12,13}, and photosensitizers for photodynamic therapy applications¹⁴. In addition, the porphyrin linked bioactive molecules have emerged as antibacterial agents with ability to induce antibiotic resistant Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria in the presence of light¹⁵. Further, porphyrin macrocycles are found useful to prevent the haemozoin production (malaria pigment) by forming a heme-drug complex through π - π interaction^{16,17}.

Triazones are an important class of nitrogen heterocycles which have been often used as amino protecting groups^{18,19}, for the preparation of polyamines,

polyfunctional amino acids and amino alcohols¹⁹. Previously, these molecules have also been utilized as creaseproofing agents for cotton, bactericides, fungicides²⁰, fibreglass binders²¹ and water soluble fertilizers^{22,23}. In the past, triazones have been synthesized²⁴ through three-component reaction of primary amines with *N,N'*-disubstituted urea and aqueous formaldehyde in the presence of a co-solvent such as dioxane or toluene. The biological significance of these two classes of compounds prompted us to develop an alternative approach towards the construction of a porphyrin-triazone system.

Thus, a novel series of *meso*-substituted triazonoporphyrins have been synthesized and characterized spectroscopically.

Results and discussion

5-(4-Aminophenyl)-10,15,20-tetraphenylporphyrin (**1**) was synthesized from *meso*-tetraphenylporphyrin according to the method as described by Meng *et al.*²⁵ and used as a starting material for the synthesis of target porphyrinic triazone analogues. The novel *meso*-substituted triazonoporphyrins (**2-6**) were prepared by the reaction of 5-(4-aminophenyl)-10,15,20-tetraphenylporphyrin with HCHO and *N,N'*-disubstituted urea or thiourea in THF at reflux temperature in a one-pot operation within 24 h (Scheme 1). The progress of the reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC). After usual workup and chromatographic purification, the desired products

Scheme 1

were obtained in 40 to 50% isolated yields. All the newly synthesized compounds were well characterized spectroscopically by using IR, NMR and mass spectrometry.

The infrared spectrum of 1,3-diethyl-5-[4-(10,15,20-triphenylporphyrin-5-yl)phenyl]-[1,3,5]triazinan-2-one (**3**) exhibited a characteristic strong absorption band at 1641 cm^{-1} due to stretching of the C=O bond. The ^1H NMR spectrum of the porphyrin **3** showed a singlet at δ 8.83 ppm for 8 β -pyrrolic protons. In addition, the characteristic signals for the 19 *meso*-phenyl protons were present as doublets and multiplets between δ 7.38–8.23 ppm. The presence of triazone moiety in the compound (**3**) was confirmed due to the presence of a singlet at δ 4.94 ppm for two CH_2 groups of the triazone ring, a quartet and a triplet at δ 3.52 and 1.23 ppm for two CH_2 and two CH_3 groups of the ethyl chain, respectively. Two internal NH protons of the porphyrin ring appeared as a singlet at δ -2.77 ppm (Fig. 1).

The high resolution mass spectrum of porphyrin (**3**) showed a molecular ion peak at m/z 770.1809 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$)⁺ which further confirmed the proposed structure. Similarly, other porphyrinic triazone derivatives (**2**, **4**, **5**, **6**) were characterized by using IR, NMR and mass spectrometry and their spectral data are presented in the Experimental section.

In summary, we have demonstrated a simple one-pot three-component methodology for the synthesis of various *meso*-substituted triazonoporphyrins which may be useful candidates for biological evaluations.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents required for the synthesis were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and Merck. The progress of the reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) on silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ (pre-coated aluminium sheets). ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were obtained in CDCl_3 on Bruker 300 MHz NMR spectrometer and Jeol ECX 400 MHz NMR spectrometer, respectively by using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in parts per million (ppm) and coupling constant (J) are reported in Hertz (Hz). Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer IR spectrometer and absorption maxima (ν_{max}) are given in cm^{-1} . Mass spectra were recorded on an ESI-MS (micromass LCT, Waters) mass spectrometer. The melting points were determined in open capillary tubes on Buchi M-560 melting point apparatus and are uncorrected.

General procedure for the synthesis of meso-substituted triazonoporphyrins (2-6) :

To a stirred solution of 5-(4-aminophenyl)-10,15,20-

Fig. 1. ^1H NMR spectrum of triazonoporphyrin (3).

tetraphenylporphyrin (50 mg, 0.07 mmol) in THF (10 ml), aqueous formaldehyde solution (37% w/v, 30 μL , 0.35 mmol) was added followed by the addition of *N,N'*-disubstituted urea or thiourea (0.11 mmol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 h. After completion of the reaction, the mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and diluted with chloroform (20 ml). The organic layer was washed with water (4×20 ml), dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified over silica gel column by using CHCl_3 /hexane as solvent.

1,3-Dimethyl-5-[4-(10,15,20-triphenylporphyrin-5-yl)-phenyl]-[1,3,5]triazinan-2-one (2) :

Purple coloured solid; yield : 40%; m.p. >200 $^\circ\text{C}$; ν_{max} (film)/ cm^{-1} : 3318, 3054, 2924, 1639, 1603, 1511, 1298, 965, 801, 731, 701; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.89–8.83 (8H, m, β -pyrrolic H), 8.22–8.20 (6H, m, *meso*-ArH), 8.13 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, *meso*-ArH), 7.76–7.74 (9H, m, *meso*-ArH), 7.35 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, *meso*-ArH), 4.95 (4H, s, $\text{N-CH}_2\text{-N}$), 3.07 (6H, s, NCH_3), -2.76 (2H, s, internal NH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 156.3, 147.4, 142.1, 136.2, 135.5, 134.5, 131.2, 131.0, 127.6, 126.6, 120.1, 120.0, 119.6, 116.9, 66.9, 32.5; HRMS (ESI) Calcd. for $\text{C}_{49}\text{H}_{40}\text{N}_7\text{O}$: 742.3294 (M +

H) $^+$; Found : 742.3358.

1,3-Diethyl-5-[4-(10,15,20-triphenylporphyrin-5-yl)-phenyl]-[1,3,5]triazinan-2-one (3) :

Purple coloured solid; yield : 50%; m.p. >200 $^\circ\text{C}$; ν_{max} (film)/ cm^{-1} : 3318, 3054, 2961, 2924, 1641, 1605, 1501, 1472, 1351, 1292, 1191, 1071, 966, 801, 750; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.83 (8H, s, β -pyrrolic H), 8.22–8.20 (6H, m, *meso*-ArH), 8.12 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, *meso*-ArH), 7.80–7.74 (9H, m, *meso*-ArH), 7.37 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, *meso*-ArH), 4.94 (4H, s, $\text{N-CH}_2\text{-N}$), 3.52 (4H, q, J 7.2 Hz, CH_2), 1.23 (6H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH_3), -2.77 (2H, s, internal NH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 154.9, 147.5, 142.1, 136.3, 135.3, 134.5, 131.0, 127.6, 126.6, 120.1, 120.0, 119.6, 117.4, 65.1, 40.0, 13.5; HRMS (ESI) Calcd. for $\text{C}_{51}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_7\text{O}$: 770.3607 (M + H) $^+$; Found : 770.1809.

1,3-Diphenyl-5-[4-(10,15,20-triphenylporphyrin-5-yl)-phenyl]-[1,3,5]triazinan-2-one (4) :

Purple coloured solid; yield : 20%; m.p. >200 $^\circ\text{C}$; ν_{max} (film)/ cm^{-1} : 3319, 3054, 3023, 2924, 2852, 1684, 1598, 1508, 1473, 1350, 1221, 966, 800, 751, 701; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 9.00–8.73 (8H, m, β -pyrrolic H), 8.49–8.21 (6H, m, *meso*-ArH), 8.05–7.95 (2H, m, *meso*-ArH), 7.85–7.65 (9H, m, *meso*-ArH), 7.57–

7.45 (2H, m, *meso*-ArH), 7.07–6.50 (10H, m, ArH), 4.87 (4H, s, N-CH₂-N), -2.77 (2H, s, internal NH); HRMS (ESI) Calcd. for C₅₉H₄₄N₇O : 866.3607 (M + H)⁺; Found : 866.4024.

5-[4-(10,15,20-Triphenylporphyrin-5-yl)-phenyl]-[1,3,5]triazinane-2-thione (5) :

Purple coloured solid; yield : 50%; m.p. >200 °C; ν_{\max} (film)/cm⁻¹ : 3318, 2924, 1685, 1598, 1508, 1351, 1221, 1178, 966, 800, 752, 701; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.93–8.84 (8H, m, β -pyrrolic H), 8.22–8.20 (6H, m, *meso*-ArH), 8.13 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, *meso*-ArH), 8.00–7.75 (9H, m, *meso*-ArH), 7.41 (2H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, *meso*-ArH), 6.77 (2H, s, NH), 4.98 (4H, s, NCH₂N), -2.78 (2H, s, internal NH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 176.4, 146.6, 142.0, 135.6, 135.5, 134.5, 134.2, 131.3, 130.0, 127.6, 127.3, 126.6, 126.3, 120.1, 117.5, 117.3, 60.7; HRMS (ESI) Calcd. for C₄₇H₃₆N₇S : 730.2753 (M+H)⁺; Found : 729.8469 (Found : C, 77.29; H, 4.92; N, 13.51. Calcd. for C₄₇H₃₅N₇S : C, 77.34; H, 4.83; N, 13.43%).

1,3-Dimethyl-5-[4-(10,15,20-triphenylporphyrin-5-yl)-phenyl]-[1,3,5]triazinane-2-thione (6) :

Purple coloured solid; yield : 60%; m.p. >200 °C; ν_{\max} (film)/cm⁻¹ : 3317, 2925, 1602, 1498, 1354, 1222, 1191, 966, 801, 751; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.95–8.84 (8H, m, β -pyrrolic H), 8.22–8.08 (8H, m, *meso*-ArH), 7.76–7.60 (9H, m, *meso*-ArH), 7.37 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, *meso*-ArH), 4.94 (4H, s, NCH₂N), 3.07 (6H, s, NCH₃), -2.76 (2H, s, internal NH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 175.9, 148.7, 143.5, 137.1, 134.6, 134.4, 132.1, 131.0, 128.4, 127.2, 121.1, 119.9, 118.6, 117.6, 65.7, 31.9; HRMS (ESI) Calcd. for C₄₉H₄₀N₇S : 758.3066 (M+H)⁺; Found : 758.3282.

Acknowledgement

We thank University of Delhi, India for providing financial support to complete this work. DKS is grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, India for Junior Research Fellowship.

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